

DELAMINATION GROWTH DURING THE INITIAL POSTBUCKLING PHASE IN COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The initial postbuckling and growth behavior of delaminations in plates is studied by a perturbation procedure. In this work, no restrictive assumptions regarding the delamination thickness and plate length are made, i.e. the usual thin film assumptions are relaxed. The perturbation procedure is based on an asymptotic expansion of the load and deformation quantities in terms of the distortion parameter of the delaminated layer, the latter being considered a compressive elastica. Closed form solutions for the load and mid-point delamination deflection versus applied compressive displacement during the initial postbuckling phase are derived. Moreover, closed form expressions for the energy-release rate and the mixity ratio (i.e. Mode II vs Mode I) at the delamination tip are produced.

Keywords: compression, delamination, growth, buckling, plate, composites

1. INTRODUCTION

The one delamination configuration most thoroughly studied is the one-dimensional delamination, consisting of a delamination in an infinitely thick plate. In this model¹, which has also been called "thin film" model, the unbuckled (base) plate is assumed to be subject to a uniform compressive strain. Closed form expressions for the energy release rate from the thin film model were derived by Chai et al¹ by using the strain energy expressions before and after delamination buckling.

The other configuration most extensively studied is the axisymmetric counterpart to the one-dimensional delamination, i.e. a circular delamination in a perfectly rigid supporting plate. The latter relates also to the so-called blister test used to determine adhesive and cohesive material properties. For this configuration, results for the energy release rate of a circular delamination were given, among others, by Chai² and calculated through a path-independent integral approach by Yin³. In the same context, Storåkers and Andersson⁴ derived general potential energy theorems and associated bounds for composite plates within the kinematical assumptions usually attributed to von Karman, and studied in detail the efficiency of different analytical and numerical means for this circular delamination case.

For delaminations in plates that cannot fulfill the "thin film" model assumptions, both the critical load and the post-critical behavior are expected to deviate from the predictions of Chai et al¹. To this extent, Simitses et al⁵ studied the critical load for a delamination of

arbitrary thickness and size in a finite plate. Their results showed indeed a range of critical load vs thin film load ratios, depending on delamination and base plate dimensions, as well as base plate end fixity (simply-supported vs clamped). Concerning the post-critical behavior of delaminations of arbitrary size, Kardomateas⁶ provided a formulation for studying the postbuckling behavior by using elastica theory for representing the deflections of the buckled layer; this work resulted in a system of nonlinear equations rather than closed form expressions. On the contrary, this paper presents a closed form solution based on an asymptotic expansion of the load and deformation quantities.

2. INITIAL POSTBUCKLING SOLUTION

In a delaminated system, which can be thought of as an aggregate of constitutive parts such as the delaminated layer and the base plate, the conditions of geometrical continuity at the common sections (i.e. where the delamination starts or ends) play a particularly important part in the realization of equilibrium states which follow non-linear paths. The exact laws that govern the behavior of single compressive elements elastically restrained at the ends by means of concentrated forces and moments constitutes the elastica theory⁷. Generalized coordinates of deformation are the distortion parameter, α , which represents the tangent rotation at an inflection point from the straight position, and the amplitude variable $\Phi(x)$. The initial postbuckling deformations are relatively small, so the exact expressions may be expanded in Taylor series in terms of the distortion parameter. Exact dependence of the end moments, end rotations and the flexural contraction is through elliptic functions; however the asymptotic expressions that will be given in this work are in terms of trigonometric functions.

Consider a plate of half-length L (and unit width) with a through-the-width delamination of half-length ℓ , symmetrically located (Fig. 1). The delamination is at an arbitrary position through the thickness T . Over the delaminated region, the laminate consists of the part above the delamination, of thickness h referred to as the "delaminated" part, and the part below the delamination, of thickness $H = T - h$, referred to as the "substrate" part. The remaining, intact laminate, of thickness T and length $b = L - \ell$, is referred to as the "base" plate. Without loss of generality, it may be assumed that $h < T/2$. Accordingly, the subscript $i = d, s, b$ refers to the delaminated part, the substrate or the base plate, respectively. In the following, we shall also denote by D_i the bending stiffness, $D_i = Et_i^3 / [12(1 - \nu^2)]$, t_i being the thickness of the corresponding part, E the modulus of elasticity and ν the Poisson's ratio. For simplicity reasons, the properties of the material are assumed homogeneous, linearly elastic and isotropic (orthotropic properties can be accounted by using $\nu_{12}\nu_{21}$ instead of ν^2 and E the modulus of elasticity along the $x \equiv 1$ axis). Notice also that in Fig. 1 the end moments and tangent rotations are assumed positive clockwise.

The buckled configuration of the delaminated layer is part of an inflectional elastica with end amplitude Φ_d and distortion parameter ϵ . At the critical state, the end amplitude is Φ_d^0 . Suppose that in the slightly buckled configuration, Φ_d can be expanded in the form:

$$\Phi_d = \Phi_d^0 + \phi_d^{(1)}\epsilon + \phi_d^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + O(\epsilon^3). \quad (1)$$

Then the end rotation at the common section θ is given by expanding the relevant expression⁷ in Taylor series in terms of ϵ (notice that at the critical state $\theta^0 = 0$):

$$\begin{aligned} \theta &= (\sin \Phi_d)\epsilon - \frac{1}{24}(\sin \Phi_d \cos^2 \Phi_d)\epsilon^3 + \dots = (\sin \Phi_d^0)\epsilon + \\ &+ (\cos \Phi_d^0)\phi_d^{(1)}\epsilon^2 + \dots = \theta^{(1)}\epsilon + \theta^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + \theta^{(3)}\epsilon^3 + O(\epsilon^4). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Definition of the geometry.

Notice that by the continuity condition, θ is the same for both the delaminated and substrate parts as well as the base plate. Similar asymptotic expansions are found for the end moment, M_d , and the axial force P_d as well as the flexural contraction, f_d . These are given in detail in Ref. 8.

Although the substrate part and the base plate undergo moderate bending with no inflection point, we may also use the elastica theory to describe their (nonlinear) deformation; in this case the inflection points are outside the actual elastic curve. For the substrate part, we have to expand not only the amplitude Φ_s , but also the distortion parameter, α_s , in a perturbation series with respect to the distortion parameter of the delaminated layer, ϵ :

$$\Phi_s = \Phi_s^0 + \phi_s^{(1)}\epsilon + \phi_s^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + O(\epsilon^3), \quad \alpha_s = \alpha_s^{(1)}\epsilon + \alpha_s^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + \alpha_s^{(3)}\epsilon^3 + O(\epsilon^4). \quad (3)$$

Then the end rotation at the common section θ is given by expanding again in Taylor series in terms of ϵ :

$$\theta = (\sin \Phi_s)\alpha_s - \frac{1}{24}(\sin \Phi_s \cos^2 \Phi_s)\alpha_s^3 + \dots = \theta_s^{(1)}\epsilon + \theta_s^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + \theta_s^{(3)}\epsilon^3 + O(\epsilon^4). \quad (4)$$

In a similar fashion, by using the expressions (3), we can write the asymptotic expansion for the end moment, M_s (again $M_s^0 = 0$) and the axial force P_s as well as the flexural contraction, f_s . The detailed expressions of $M_d^{(k)}$, $\theta_s^{(k)}$, $M_s^{(k)}$, $P_s^{(k)}$ and $f_s^{(k)}$ are again given in Kardomateas⁸.

The base plate is assumed to be simply supported, so at the simply-supported end, the amplitude $\Phi = -\pi/2$, and at the common section $\Phi = \Phi_b$. The amplitude at the common section and the distortion parameter of the base plate are now expanded in terms of the distortion parameter of the delaminated part ϵ :

$$\Phi_b = \Phi_b^0 + \phi_b^{(1)}\epsilon + \phi_b^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + O(\epsilon^3), \quad \alpha_b = \alpha_b^{(1)}\epsilon + \alpha_b^{(2)}\epsilon^2 + \alpha_b^{(3)}\epsilon^3 + O(\epsilon^4). \quad (5)$$

Moreover, the end rotation at the common section θ , is given by expanding again the relevant expression from Britvek⁷ in Taylor series in terms of ϵ . Expressions for the end moment, M_b , the axial force at the base plate (which is also the applied force), and the flexural contraction, f_b , between the simply-supported end and the common section are

similarly obtained. These expressions are again defined in Ref. 8.

Having obtained the asymptotic expressions for the force and deformation quantities, we shall discuss the formulation of the equilibrium and compatibility requirements that will ultimately define the non-linear post-critical path. Force and moment equilibrium at the common section require:

$$P_d + P_s - P = 0, \quad M_d + M_s + M_b - P_d \frac{H}{2} + P_s \frac{h}{2} = 0. \quad (6)$$

The deflections of the delaminated and substrate parts should be geometrically compatible. Thus, a second condition necessary for a solution involves the compatible shortening of the delaminated and substrate parts, which consists, in turn, of the compressive and flexural shortening:

$$\left(f_d + 2 \frac{P_d \ell}{Eh} \right) - \left(f_s + 2 \frac{P_s \ell}{EH} \right) + \theta T = 0. \quad (7)$$

As the compressive load P is applied, the plate remains flat and a primary state solution (pure compression) is characterized by $P^0 = P_d^0 T/h$ and $P_s^0 = P_d^0 H/h$.

Although determination of the critical point is not a primary objective of this paper and the buckling analysis has been thoroughly carried out in other works (e.g. Ref. 5), we shall briefly describe the equations for the critical point (in terms of Φ_d^0) for the sake of completeness, and because the formulation for the initial postbuckling naturally follows that for the critical point.

By equating the first order rotation at the common section, we obtain $\alpha_s^{(1)}$ and $\alpha_b^{(1)}$: $\alpha_s^{(1)} = \sin \Phi_d^0 / \sin \Phi_s^0$ and $\alpha_b^{(1)} = \sin \Phi_d^0 / \beta$

Writing the moment equilibrium (6) and the geometric compatibility (7) for the first order terms, and eliminating the quantity $[P_d^{(1)} H - P_s^{(1)} h]$ leads to the characteristic equation, for the determination of Φ_d^0 :

$$\frac{D_d}{\ell} \Phi_d^0 \cos \Phi_d^0 + \sin \Phi_d^0 \left[\frac{D_s}{\ell} \Phi_s^0 \cot \Phi_s^0 + \frac{D_b}{b} \left(\Phi_b^0 + \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \frac{\cos \Phi_b^0}{\beta} + \frac{EThH}{4\ell} \right] = 0. \quad (8)$$

Next, the initial postbuckling behavior is considered.

2.1 First and Second Order Forces

Force equilibrium, eq (6) for the first order terms, and use of the asymptotic expressions for the first order forces gives

$$\phi_b^{(1)} = \frac{\Phi_d^0}{\Phi_b^0 + (\pi/2)} \frac{D_d b^2}{D_b \ell^2} \phi_d^{(1)} + \frac{\Phi_s^0}{\Phi_b^0 + (\pi/2)} \frac{D_s b^2}{D_b \ell^2} \phi_s^{(1)} = \rho_d \phi_d^{(1)} + \rho_s \phi_s^{(1)}. \quad (9a)$$

By equating the second order terms in the expressions for the slope at the common section, $\theta^{(2)}$, and using (9a) we can find $\alpha_s^{(2)}$ and $\alpha_b^{(2)}$ as follows:

$$\alpha_s^{(2)} = \gamma_d \phi_d^{(1)} + \gamma_s \phi_s^{(1)}, \quad \alpha_b^{(2)} = \eta_d \phi_d^{(1)} + \eta_s \phi_s^{(1)}. \quad (9b)$$

Determination of the first order forces requires deriving $\phi_d^{(1)}$ and $\phi_s^{(1)}$ and this will be discussed next. The moment equilibrium equation (6) for the second order terms is

$$M_d^{(2)} + M_s^{(2)} + M_b^{(2)} = \frac{1}{2} [P_d^{(2)} H - P_s^{(2)} h]. \quad (10)$$

The geometric compatibility equation (7) for the second order terms gives:

$$f_d^{(2)} - f_s^{(2)} + \theta^{(2)}T = \left[P_s^{(2)}h - P_d^{(2)}H \right] \frac{2\ell}{EhH}. \quad (11)$$

Eliminating the quantity $\left[P_s^{(2)}h - P_d^{(2)}H \right]$ from the previous two equations gives one linear equation for $\phi_d^{(1)}$ and $\phi_s^{(1)}$.

The second equation needed to find $\phi_d^{(1)}$ and $\phi_s^{(1)}$ is the first order geometric compatibility equation (7) at the common section, which becomes a linear equation for $\phi_d^{(1)}$ and $\phi_s^{(1)}$ after the expressions for the first order delamination and substrate forces, and the one for the first order rotation, are substituted. These two linear equations allow finding $\phi_d^{(1)}$ and $\phi_s^{(1)}$, and hence the first order forces $P_d^{(1)}$, $P_s^{(1)}$ and the first order applied force $P^{(1)} = P_d^{(1)} + P_s^{(1)}$.

Second order forces are determined in a similar fashion. Determination of the second order forces requires deriving $\phi_d^{(2)}$ and $\phi_s^{(2)}$ and this is accomplished by using the moment equilibrium equation (6) and the geometric compatibility equation (7) for the third order terms. Moreover, $\alpha_s^{(3)}$ is found by using second order force equilibrium and equating the third order terms in the expressions for the slope at the common section of the delaminated and the substrate parts, $\theta^{(3)}$, and $\alpha_b^{(3)}$ is determined by equating the third order terms in the expressions for the slope at the common section for the delaminated and the base parts⁸.

The expressions during the initial postbuckling stage for two additional quantities, which are typically needed for correlation with experimental data: the mid-point deflection of the delaminated layer and the substrate part, and the applied compressive displacement (or applied strain) are discussed in Ref. 8.

3. DELAMINATION GROWTH CHARACTERISTICS

Before applying the initial postbuckling solution that has just been presented, the basic, interface crack solutions that are needed in the analysis will be reviewed. The formulas of Hutchinson and Suo⁹ will be presented with the homogeneous material assumption into consideration.

For the plane-strain interface crack shown in Fig. 1, the energy release rate G is :

$$G = \frac{1 - \nu}{4\mu} \left[\frac{P^{*2}}{Ah} + \frac{M^{*2}}{Ih^3} + 2 \frac{P^*M^*}{\sqrt{AI}h^2} \sin \gamma \right]. \quad (12)$$

where μ is the shear modulus. P^* and M^* are linear combinations of the loads from the previous postbuckling solution: $P^* = P_d - C_1P - C_2M_b/h$ and $M^* = M_d - C_3M_b$. Moreover, A and I are positive dimensionless numbers and the angle γ is restricted such that $\gamma \leq \pi/2$. The preceding formula does not separate the opening and shearing components. Instead, the following two expressions give the Mode I and Mode II stress intensity factors:

$$K_I = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\frac{P^*}{\sqrt{Ah}} \cos \omega + \frac{M^*}{\sqrt{Ih^3}} \sin(\omega + \gamma) \right], \quad (13a)$$

$$K_{II} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\frac{P^*}{\sqrt{Ah}} \sin \omega - \frac{M^*}{\sqrt{Ih^3}} \cos(\omega + \gamma) \right]. \quad (13b)$$

The quantity ω varies slowly with $\eta = h/H$ in the entire range $0 \leq \eta \leq 1$ with the approximate formula⁹: $\omega = 52.1^0 - 3^0\eta$. The mode mixity is defined by

$$\psi = \tan^{-1}(K_{II}/K_I) . \quad (14)$$

Substituting the asymptotic expressions for the forces and moments from the postbuckling solution already presented, gives

$$P^* = \epsilon P^{*(1)} + \epsilon^2 P^{*(2)} + \dots \quad M^* = \epsilon M^{*(1)} + \epsilon^2 M^{*(2)} + \dots \quad (15)$$

Notice that the zero order quantities in the expression for P^* cancel out.

In the previous relations, the first and second order forces and moments, $P_d^{(k)}$, $P_s^{(k)}$, $M_d^{(k)}$, $M_b^{(k)}$, $k = 1, 2$ have already been found from the initial postbuckling solution described in the previous section.

Now the energy release rate and the Mode I and II stress intensity factors can be written in the form:

$$G = \epsilon^2 G^{(2)} + \epsilon^3 G^{(3)} + \dots ; \quad K_{I,II} = \epsilon K_{I,II}^{(1)} + \epsilon^2 K_{I,II}^{(2)} + \dots , \quad (16)$$

where $K_{I,II}^{(1)}$, $K_{I,II}^{(2)}$ are found by substituting in (13) the first or second order forces and moments, respectively, $G^{(2)}$ is found from (12) by substituting directly the first order forces and moments, and $G^{(3)}$ is given explicitly in Ref. 8.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

For an illustration of the results from the previous analysis, consider a delaminated plate with $E = 10$ GPa and $\nu = 0.3$ and delamination and plate length $\ell = 20$ mm and $L = 60$ mm, respectively, and delamination thickness $h = 0.4$ mm. These dimensions correspond to our specimen dimensions (a width of 10 mm has also been considered and is appropriately accounted in the results). To keep the critical strain ϵ_{cr} constant, we keep the delamination length and thickness constant and vary only the plate thickness to get a varying ratio h/T ; this would ensure the same thin film model solution.

Fig. 2 shows the energy release rate $(2G/Eh)10^5$, as a function of the applied strain for $h/T = 0.10$ and $h/T = 0.30$. It is seen that for the same applied strain, the energy release rate for the case of the delamination located further away from the surface ($h/T = 0.3$) is always higher than the one for the delamination close to the surface ($h/T = 0.1$). In the beginning, i.e. for relatively small applied strain, the curves tend toward the thin film solution for a decreasing ratio h/T (as expected); however as the applied strain is increased, the thin film model solution rises even above the $h/T = 0.3$ solution and predicts a much higher energy release rate. Experimental results that have been previously reported by Kardomateas¹⁰ confirm clearly the reduced growth resistance of the "large ratio" case, $h/T = 0.3$, versus the "small ratio" one, $h/T=0.1$. In fact the "small ratio" delamination in these studies did not grow at all despite a very large increase in the applied strain. Notice that this important difference in growth behavior cannot obviously be predicted by the thin film model, which, because of its strongly nonlinearly increasing $G - \epsilon_0$ curve, would predict growth even for the "small ratio" delamination if the applied strain would be sufficiently increased.

Another very interesting result is the variation of the mode mixity (Mode II versus Mode I) at the delamination tip. Fig. 3 shows the mode mixity ψ versus applied strain. It is seen that for the same applied strain, the delamination located further away from the

Fig. 2. Energy release rate, $(2G/Eh)10^5$, as a function of the applied strain.

surface ($h/T = 0.3$) shows a higher mode I proportion than the one close to the surface ($h/T = 0.1$). As a consequence, the value of the applied strain at which the delamination tip loading becomes pure Mode II ($\psi = -90^\circ$) is increased. This point for the thin film model is at $\epsilon_0/\epsilon_{cr} = 7.55$. The curves show a trend toward the thin film solution for a decreasing ratio h/T .

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Fig. 3. Mode mixity, ψ^0 , versus applied strain.

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